

ACADEMIC COLLABORATIONS AND PUBLIC HEALTH: LESSONS FROM DUTCH UNIVERSITIES' TOBACCO INDUSTRY PARTNERSHIPS FOR FOSSIL FUEL TIES

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ABSTRACT

Tobacco and fossil fuels are both leading commercial drivers of mortality, yet academic collaboration with these industries is treated differently. While the WHO and many academics recognise an “*irreconcilable conflict*” between the tobacco industry and public health interests, many universities justify fossil fuel collaborations if linked to the energy transition.

This report draws lessons from the history of tobacco industry collaborations in the Netherlands to inform current debates on fossil fuel ties in academia. We examine the evolving policies and attitudes toward tobacco in the Netherlands, the industry’s historical and ongoing influence on academia, and parallels with fossil fuel strategies—such as casting doubt on health risks, leveraging industry-funded research, shifting blame, and emphasising consumer responsibility and economic importance.

Key findings include:

1. We initially expected that university action would have played a leading role in tobacco control efforts. Instead, we found that Dutch universities followed, rather than led, shifts in public opinion on tobacco, with weaker resistance from health professionals compared to countries like the UK.
2. Other parts of the academic ecosystem, namely medical journals and cancer research funders, have implemented policies that set de facto boundaries.
3. While attitudes towards tobacco industry collaborations shifted, Dutch universities lack explicit policies restricting such partnerships.
4. Dutch academic ties to the tobacco industry have persisted in recent years through direct and indirect funding structures, including partnerships mediated via health-tech firms partially owned by tobacco companies.
5. Many researchers remain unaware of how industries exploit academic affiliations to delay policy action and shape public perception.

Given the major public health burden posed by both tobacco and fossil fuels — through smoking-related diseases, air pollution, and climate change — and their continued influence via the academic world, universities, research funders, journals and medical professionals should critically assess their engagement with these industries.

Policy recommendations

1. Increase transparency on industry ties, including both direct and indirect funding, to ensure informed decision-making.
2. Encourage journals and research funders to develop policies around fossil fuel involvement, similar to those adopted by so-called ‘tobacco-free’ journals and funders.
3. Educate researchers and students on industry tactics aimed at delaying regulation and policy change, for instance by integrating this into mandatory ethics training.
4. Phase out fossil fuel industry influence in research agenda-setting, research consortia, and public funding programs.
5. Critically evaluate new research collaborations with the fossil fuel industry, particularly on energy transition and sustainability projects, to avoid conflicts of interest.
6. Task an independent body with monitoring and researching industry tactics, ensuring academic policies remain aligned with public health and climate goals.

As universities refine their external partnership policies, they have an opportunity to align their approach across harmful industries, safeguard academic integrity, and contribute to a healthier and more sustainable society.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and relevance

The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified four major industries as key contributors to the global burden of non-communicable diseases (NCD's), such as cardiovascular diseases, cancers and diabetes: tobacco, ultra-processed foods, fossil fuels, and alcohol. The commercial products of these sectors are responsible for an estimated 2.7 million deaths annually in Europe, as well as for 19 million deaths globally. This accounts for 34% of all global deaths [1, 2].

The WHO identifies influence from major commercial industries as a major barrier to implementing NCD-related policies and regulations [1]. Key tactics involve marketing, using corporate social responsibility (CSR) programmes to deflect criticism and promote industry-friendly public health strategies, lobbying and casting doubt on evidence. Industry also uses strategies to exert influence via the academic world, such as influencing the scientific process, funding industry-friendly research and associating themselves with academics and respected institutions to improve their public image, build trust among professionals and policymakers, and gain influence [1]. Industry-funded scientific research resulting from these collaborations often brings significant conflicts of interest [3].

Here, we investigate investigate industry collaborations with Dutch universities. Today, academic collaboration with the tobacco industry is widely regarded as inappropriate in the Netherlands, due to the public consensus on the harms of smoking and the well-documented influence the tobacco industry had on science[4]. There is growing concern about collaborations with the fossil fuel industry, illustrated by several university occupations since the end of 2022 [5, 6, 7] and dialogues at almost all Dutch universities [8, 9, 10]. However, almost all Dutch academic institutions continue to collaborate with oil and gas companies [11].

There appears to be a difference between how tobacco industry collaborations and fossil fuel industry collaborations are evaluated. For example, in 2017-2018, a tobacco industry-funded research project at Utrecht University generated significant controversy. Following public pressure, the university chose to return the funding and independently finance the research. Rector Bert Van der Zwaan told the newspaper *Volkscrant*: "As a university, we are deeply embedded in society; we listen to societal voices, even when criticism is expressed" [12, 13]. In contrast, the university started new collaborations with fossil fuel companies TotalEnergies, BP and RWE in 2024, which according to the university were already (orally) agreed upon before the university's 2023 statement to "only enter into research collaborations with fossil companies and organizations if they are intensively and demonstrably committed to accelerating the energy transition, in line with the Paris Climate Agreement" [14, 15, 16]. One of these new collaborations involves Prof. Petra de Jongh (see also Appendix A), who receives €1.5 million from BP for a research project on liquid fuels. She justified the partnership by stating: "BP is one of the top-four major oil companies in terms of climate. The company is making major investments in renewable energy. This is a company we can work with." The Executive Board found the choice for BP "convincing" [16].

A broader tolerance toward fossil fuel partnerships was also evident during a 2023 debate on corporate collaborations, where Prof. Yvonne van der Meer of Maastricht University commented: "No university will enter into a partnership with the tobacco industry, but we shouldn't immediately rule out fossil fuel companies" [17]. Notably, Saudi Arabian oil company Aramco funds the research chair Sustainability of Chemicals and Materials, currently held by Prof. van der Meer, at the Aachen-Maastricht Institute for Biobased Materials—a joint initiative between Maastricht University, RWTH Aachen University, and Fraunhofer IME. In a 2024 article published by *Follow the Money (FTM)*, the rector of Maastricht University stated that it is "conceivable that no permission would be granted for a side activity at Philip Morris International or British American Tobacco" [18]. However, ancillary activities with fossil fuel companies are not (yet) regarded as problematic by university boards. According to the Mapping Fossil Ties database, between 2022 and 2025, 17 Dutch research chairs were funded by the fossil fuel industry and 17 staff, board or committee members at Dutch academic institutions held additional roles with organisations in the fossil fuel industry (see Appendix A) [19]. In the Netherlands, externally financed professorships (so-called "bijzondere hoogleraren") are common. Research of *Financieel Dagblad (FD)* in 2022-2023 exposed that 1 in 5 professors in the Netherlands were externally funded [20]. Government funding of universities has been receding and Dutch universities and researchers are actively stimulated to look for external funding to fill the funding gap and conduct research that best aligns with the priorities of the government and the business sector [21].

During a discussion organised by the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) in November 2024, a researcher said: *“Collaboration with certain partners inevitably comes at the expense of your credibility as a scientist. For example, if you conduct health research for cigarette manufacturer Philip Morris or if, as a food researcher, you receive sponsorship from McDonald’s and Coca-Cola, you are not seen as credible. Society views collaborations with fossil fuel companies in the same way, but researchers are much slower to respond to this societal shift”* [22].

The VU Amsterdam is the only Dutch university to date (April 2025) which has finalised a policy excluding new research collaborations with fossil fuel industry which do not *“demonstrably commit, in the short term, to the objectives of the Paris Climate Agreement”* [23, 24]. Utrecht University announced in July 2023 its intention to implement a similar policy; however, its assessment framework for fossil fuel industry collaborations is characterised by notable exceptions [25]. Eight other universities have formed or are forming policies for stricter guidelines around fossil collaborations, however, many of them evaluate whether the research topics are desirable rather than assessing the collaboration partners [19]. Universities face challenges in determining the criteria for evaluating research projects, and critics advocate for assessments at the partner level due to concerns such as the risks of greenwashing [26], steering the direction and conclusions of research and therefore the energy transition [27], and bolstering a social licence to operate for the sector [28] - the latter two being concerns for working with the tobacco industry as well [29].

After the VU Amsterdam banned research partnerships with fossil fuel partners in 2023, initially hesitant staff members—some of whom had actively opposed the decision—later expressed support and pride in the university’s leadership. This shift was attributed both to clearer messaging over time and the human tendency to align with an established status quo. WHO guidelines on collaborations with the tobacco industry were also referenced by staff in arguments urging the VU to take a similar stance on fossil fuel partnerships—a strategy that proved effective, as key stakeholders later acknowledged it had a significant impact on their thinking [30]. Further, the action taken by universities as a result of pressure from a relatively small group of students and staff precipitated university-wide discussions where the community was forced to engage with the issue. A survey at TU Delft in 2024, in which approximately 10% of the academic community participated, found that 87% of respondents had never previously expressed views on fossil fuel collaborations. Despite the university’s strong ties to the fossil fuel industry, only 17% of respondents recommended against taking measures to limit collaboration [31]. These examples show that taking (policy) action itself can drive attitudinal change.

1.2 Research question and hypothesis

In light of current debates about fossil fuel ties, we set out to investigate the history and current state of collaborations with the tobacco industry in the Netherlands. In this brief study, we examined the changing nature of scientific collaborations with the tobacco industry in the Netherlands and what influence—if any—actions by Dutch universities had on national tobacco control efforts.

We hypothesised that universities’ policies would have played a leading role in the perception of collaborations with the tobacco industry, contributing to broader tobacco control efforts and, ultimately, to public health improvements.

By examining the nature and evolution of university policies and collaborations, the study aims to identify lessons that may inform current debates around university ties to the fossil fuel industry.

1.3 Research questions

To guide our investigation, we addressed the following research questions:

- Which factors influenced tobacco control in the Netherlands, and what role, if any, did academic institutions play?
- Which policies are in place regarding academic collaboration with the tobacco industry?
- Have there been recent collaborations between academic institutions and the tobacco industry in the Netherlands?
- What factors contributed to the increased scrutiny of academic ties to the tobacco industry?
- What parallels and contrasts are there to the fossil fuel industry?

Figure 1: Smoking rate of adults in the Netherlands (18 years old or older). Source: [36] Trimbos, *Collecting data on tobacco use in the Netherlands, 2023*.

1.4 Methodology

This study presents a synthesis of existing literature, information requests to Dutch universities, and our own research and discussions on academic collaborations with the fossil fuel industry. To check for recent direct ties with the tobacco industry, we searched on Google Scholar for: "<company name> <university name>". We limited the search to the tobacco producers that are most important in the Netherlands: Philip Morris International, British American Tobacco, Imperial Brands and Japan Tobacco International (including its foundation JTI Foundation) [32].

We consulted leading Dutch tobacco control experts, Marc Willemsen and Wanda de Kanter, for background information and guidance on finding information about tobacco control policy in the Netherlands and the role of universities in this field. Section 2 draws mainly from Marc Willemsen's book 'Tobacco Control Policy in the Netherlands' (2018) [32], while Sections 3 and 4 rely heavily on investigative journalism, and research from TabakNee, an initiative from the Foundation Youth Smoking Prevention (Rookpreventie Jeugd), because there is little academic research on this topic. To determine whether there is policy in place around collaboration with the tobacco industry, we contacted the Dutch Research Council (NWO), Universiteiten van Nederland and all 15 universities affiliated with them (see Appendix B).

1.5 Report structure

In Section 2, we provide an overview of the evolution of tobacco policy in the Netherlands, offering context for the current landscape of smoking and tobacco-related issues, as well as the potential role academia may have played in this history. Section 3 examines the ongoing existence of collaborations with the tobacco industry, explores the policies universities may have in place, and analyses the factors that have contributed to the reduced social acceptance of such partnerships. Section 4 draws parallels between the tobacco and the fossil fuel industry and lists key differences. Finally, Sections 5 and 6 present recommendations for universities and suggestions for further research based on these.

2 FACTORS INFLUENCING TOBACCO CONTROL IN THE NETHERLANDS

According to the WHO, "the main influence on each country's tobacco use trend is the effort the country invests in tobacco control" [33]. Since the 1980s, the Netherlands has taken increasingly strict measures to curb tobacco use, such as banning advertising and smoking in public places, and raising taxes and the legal age of purchase. While this has led to reduced smoking rates, 19% of the Dutch population over 18 smoked in 2023 (Figure 1) [34]. Smoking remains the leading behavioural determinant of illness and death, with 7.6% of the total disease burden attributable to smoking [35].

Influences on tobacco control policy, and hence smoking behaviour and public health, have come from industry lobbies, health organisations in civic society, and international pressure. In the upcoming section, we draw mainly from Marc Willemsen's book "Tobacco Control Policy in the Netherlands" [32].

2.1 Industry lobbying

Since the 1960s, tobacco industry lobbying has been extensive and effective: delaying action in the 1970s, toning down mandatory warnings on cigarette packets in the 1980s, and changing the Dutch government position on the European Commission's minimum taxation proposal in 2009 - to name a few concrete successes [32]. When close contacts, regular meetings, and input during the policy drafting were allowed, the tobacco industry was able to have significant influence on policy making, pushing the main arguments of individual choice for the consumer, economic importance for the government, and self-regulation for the industry. The latter did not work: the "gentlemen's agreement" of 1965 to not advertise positive health claims of cigarettes was broken in 1976 by the industry, and self-regulation of advertising agreed in 1990 was also ineffective [37, 38].

The Dutch trade organisation VNO-NCW played a large role: when Dutch health minister Borst-Eilers prepared to revise the Tobacco Act in 1994-5, Alexander Rinnooy Kan (then VNO-NCW chair, earlier rector magnificus of Erasmus University Rotterdam and later economics and business administration professor at University of Amsterdam as well as a senator in the Dutch parliament) sent her a letter informing her that they saw "*no place for a paternalistic national government*" [39]. He sent the minister of economic affairs a copy of a lecture of his, arguing for the right of corporations to give "*commercial information*", and that "*the time has passed when some still thought that advertisements encourage consumers to consumptive behaviour against their will*" [40]. This is contradicted by the 1975 Health Council report noting that "*there is no real freedom of choice vis-a-vis smoking or not*" - both because of the "*social norms, the intrusive advertising*" as well as that "*pharmacological factors*", i.e. nicotine dependency, maintain the status quo of smoking [41].

The former doctor Borst-Eilers was able to push through an amendment of the Tobacco Act, but the accession of the ex-VNO-NCW lobbyist Edith Schippers to the position of Minister of Health, Welfare and Sport in 2010 led to dismantling of much tobacco control regulation, and ending subsidies for STIVORO (the national organisation for tobacco control) in 2011 leading to its close 2 years later [32].

Article 5.3 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (WHO FCTC), which entered into force for the Netherlands in 2005, requires that "*in setting and implementing their public health policies with respect to tobacco control, Parties shall act to protect these policies from commercial and other vested interests of the tobacco industry in accordance with national law.*" The WHO guidelines for implementation of Article 5.3 recommend measures that "*aim at protecting against interference not only by the tobacco industry but also, as appropriate, by organizations and individuals that work to further the interests of the tobacco industry*" [42].

However, VNO-NCW still represents the interests of the tobacco industry in dealings with parliament. Niek Jan van Kesteren, general director in 2012, acknowledged lobbying for the tobacco industry and described themselves as "*one of the few friends the tobacco industry has*" [43]. For example, despite being excluded from direct negotiations over the *Nationaal Preventieakkoord* - a Dutch national prevention agreement aimed at reducing smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, and obesity [44] - the tobacco industry managed to exert indirect influence through VNO-NCW and the CBL (Dutch Retailers Association), with the result that tax increases were delayed and a ban on the visible display of cigarettes was softened in the *Rookakkoord* (smoking prevention agreement) of 2018 [45]. On a European level, enforcement of Article 5.3 of the FCTC remains inconsistent, allowing the industry to retain influence within the European Commission despite existing regulations [46, 47].

2.2 Health professionals and charities

In contrast to these lobbying efforts by the tobacco industry, a number of health professionals and charities have played a key role in advancing tobacco control and public health in the Netherlands. Willemsen regards 1964 as the year when "*serious concerns about smoking stirred the Dutch nation and health organisations like the Dutch Cancer Society got actively involved with tobacco control*". This happened after a report from the US Public Health Service "*clearly establishes an association between cigarette smoking and substantially higher death rates*" [48]. A Dutch national organisation for tobacco control, STIVORO, was founded in 1974 and brought together the voices of three charities on their board to present a unified front to counter the tobacco lobby. It also provided continuity to combat what Willemsen calls "institutional amnesia" - the knowledge loss that comes from the high turnover of decision-makers in a democracy such as the Netherlands.

STIVORO coordinated health advocacy organisations, organised successful media campaigns and counter-campaigns, for example heading off a campaign by Philipp Morris to cast doubt on the harm of passive smoking in 1996. Nevertheless, the foundation had less access to the policymaking process than the tobacco lobby, and less resources for lobbying and legal battles. A dependence on government funding made it difficult to criticise the government (a problem also faced by its counterpart ASH in the UK), and a confrontational approach in the face of an industry-friendly government after 2007 led to its funding being cut in 2011 [32].

Willemsen describes the Dutch medical community's stance on tobacco control as "passive", and suggests this may be due to high rates of smoking among doctors as well as lobbying, for example through magazines distributed to family practitioners [32]. While the *Medische Alliantie tegen het Roken* (Medical Alliance Against Smoking) was set up in 1993, it was closed in 2008, in part due to lack of interest. In the United Kingdom, by contrast, stronger advocacy by medical organisations led to more decisive action, such as anti-tobacco advertisements. The English Health Education Council ran confrontational and effective advertising campaigns on the deadly effects of smoking and the myth of "safer" cigarettes in the 1970's. The Royal College of Physicians and the British Medical Association were vocal in their advocacy for tobacco control [32].

Individuals in the medical profession and research did engage in advocacy: university professors of public health such as Johan Mackenbach [49] and Marc Willemsen [50] have vocally called for stricter measures. Medical professionals Wanda de Kanter and Pauline Dekker have been influential in raising public awareness about the harms of tobacco use and advocating for stronger tobacco control policies [51]. Notably, the most ambitious tobacco control measures in the Netherlands were introduced by a former medical doctor, health minister Els Borst-Meijers.

2.3 International influence

What happened beyond the borders of the Netherlands also affected national policy: State Secretary Hans Simons (State secretary of well being, public health and culture from 1989 to 1994) argued for a stricter code of conduct on advertising citing stricter policy in the UK and Denmark; the political party Christen-Democratisch Appèl (CDA) argued for banning smoking in public places in 1980 following the example of France; and Minister Borst-Eilers' visit to the US and encounter with successful tobacco control policy in 1995 inspired her own proposals for tobacco policy.

International agreements were also decisive: the Netherlands had agreed to oppose the EU tobacco advertising ban as long as it was not the decisive vote; when this became the case when the UK withdrew its opposition in 1997, the Netherlands followed suit. Significantly, the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) agreement which the Netherlands signed in 2005 meant that the Dutch exemption to smoking in small cafés could be challenged in court successfully in 2014 [52]. Despite being originally ignored by tobacco control groups, who saw it more relevant to "third-world countries", it became instrumental in the Netherlands as this was "the first time anywhere in the world that a national court decided that an FCTC requirement outranked a contradictory national law" [32].

2.4 The limited influence of Dutch universities

We had initially expected that, because scientists were the ones first showing a link between tobacco and cancer, scientific institutions would also have been leading the way on tobacco control. However, there does not appear to have been a coordinated effort from Dutch universities in terms of tobacco policy advocacy. Individuals, mainly active in public health research, have attempted to use their influence to reach the general public. Universities have worked with STIVORO on knowledge dissemination around the dangers of smoking, but rarely on tobacco control advocacy [32]. Since 2013, there is a *Netherlands Network of Tobacco Control Researchers* which includes researchers working on tobacco control, with an annual conference and a research prize [53].

Rather, it is the tobacco industry that seems to have had influence on the universities. A letter from the *Nationale Jongerenraad voor Milieu en Ontwikkeling* (National Youth Council for Environment and Development) to the CDA House of Representatives faction notes that at the 1993 anniversary celebration of Erasmus University Rotterdam "Lucky Strike was the primary sponsor and let that be known with big signs" as well as running games to win a pack of

cigarettes. The Rotterdam Student Corps was sponsored by Gauloises in 1996, and at a Leiden University introduction fair for new students around that time, the organisers promoted the sponsor "Lucky Strike" on their jumpers [54].

We discuss recent academic collaboration with the tobacco industry in Section 3.4.

3 DUTCH ACADEMIC COLLABORATION WITH THE TOBACCO INDUSTRY

The tobacco industry has a long history of using academic legitimacy to spread disinformation, withholding data or publishing false or misleading data, industry-capture of journals to subvert the peer review process, paying for misleading science, hiding behind front groups to bypass bans, and attacking scientists publishing science dangerous for the industry [55].

Universities – both worldwide and in the Netherlands – have historically collaborated with the tobacco industry, including accepting funding from tobacco companies. In this chapter, we explore whether collaborations between academic institutions and the tobacco industry still exist in the Netherlands, the nature of these collaborations, and the factors that have contributed to their decline.

3.1 International university policy on tobacco industry collaborations

Several academic institutions in the US, South Africa and Australia formulated policy around collaboration with the tobacco industry. Harvard's School of Public Health formulated a policy in 2002 to "not to accept any grant or anything else of value from any tobacco manufacturer, distributor, or other tobacco-related company." According to *The Wire*, the policy was updated in 2004 to add that "prohibition will apply to funding from companies that make or market tobacco products or from entities supported by such companies" [56, 57]. Also the Ohio State University College of Public Health [58], the University of Pittsburgh School of Medicine [59], the University of Cape Town [60], and several Australian universities [61] do not accept funds from the tobacco industry.

University of California San Francisco (UCSF) faculty voted to refuse tobacco industry funding in 2003 "to put into policy what has been a practice at UCSF for years" [62]. Interestingly, the University of California has a policy that explicitly states it does *not* ban the solicitation or acceptance of research funding from tobacco companies or their affiliates [63].

In the UK, charities who fund health research such as Cancer Research UK and the Wellcome Trust have policies distancing themselves from tobacco-funded research and researchers [64, 65]. A joint statement by Cancer Research UK and Universities UK (an organisation representing the interests of UK universities) hints that tobacco funding could "compromise the independence or integrity" of teaching and research, as well as the universities' reputations, but stops short of advising universities not to accept tobacco funding. While this statement was interpreted by news outlets as a ban on tobacco funding [66], a policy from the University of Reading from 2017 contradicts this, claiming that there is "no legal basis for... a blanket restriction on dealing with tobacco companies" and that "the University will make a decision on whether to engage with a tobacco company on a case by case basis" [67].

3.2 Lack of policies on Dutch research collaboration with the tobacco industry

We found no policies regarding collaborations with the tobacco industry on the websites of Dutch universities and academic institutions. Therefore, we reached out to the Dutch Research Council (NWO), Universiteiten van Nederland, and all 15 affiliated universities to inquire whether they have such a policy in place (see Appendix B). Nine of these institutions responded: TU Eindhoven, Maastricht University, Leiden University, Utrecht University, TU Delft, University of Twente, VU Amsterdam, University of Humanistic Studies, and Universiteiten van Nederland. All confirmed that they have no explicit policy prohibiting research collaborations with the tobacco industry.

Staff from the VU noted that while no formal policy exists, collaboration with the tobacco and arms industries would not align with their core values.

Utrecht University stated that following internal debate and the eventual rejection of a research project funded by Philip Morris in 2018, each faculty established or adapted a committee to assess third-party collaborations based on ethical considerations, including potential conflicts of interest. In 2019, the university introduced a checklist to further scrutinise collaborations for ethical and integrity concerns. While Utrecht University is currently developing

a new comprehensive research assessment framework that explicitly mentions the tobacco industry, this has not yet been formalised into policy. The proposed framework states that collaboration with the tobacco industry and arms and defence industry always needs to be approved by the Executive Board and that the chances for approval are minimal.

The University of Humanistic Studies let us know that the recently installed commission for (sensitive) collaborations advised the Executive Board to look beyond human rights violations, namely also at the tobacco industry and “parties that cause damage to the climate”.

3.3 Implicit norms against tobacco industry collaboration

While Dutch universities do not have explicit policies prohibiting collaboration with the tobacco industry, the prevailing view is that such partnerships are generally considered unacceptable. This is illustrated by a 2023 statement from a Maastricht University professor, who remarked, “No university will enter into a partnership with the tobacco industry, but we shouldn’t immediately rule out fossil fuel companies” [17].

Maastricht University declared to the WHO in a grant application that they don’t work with the tobacco industry [68]. However, a professor at Maastricht University sees no issue with advising PlatoScience, a company partially owned by the tobacco industry. Researchers from the Investigative Desk and the BMJ quoted him saying: “As long as British American Tobacco does not interfere with my scientific work, I see no immediate problem.” The university told the journalists that this collaboration with PlatoScience “is not a collaboration with the tobacco industry” [68].

In 2021, Philip Morris International (PMI) acquired Vectura, a company specialising in inhaler-based drug delivery [69, 70]. This created both ethical and practical dilemmas for a Dutch research group that had signed a 4-year agreement with Vectura in 2018. The researchers published an article explaining their personal perspective on how this acquisition affected their research [71]. The fact that they were suddenly affiliated with a tobacco company brought them “deep moral concern”. They used the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity to weigh their options and concluded that continuation of the agreement may be more favourable than termination - particularly motivated by the project’s relevance and their sense of responsibility to complete it. The main obstacle was that respiratory journals would not accept papers reporting work funded by tobacco companies.¹ The researchers emphasised: “Given the tobacco industry’s historical involvement in manipulating and funding research(ers) to deceive consumers regarding the harmful effects of smoking, it is difficult to ensure the independence of tobacco-funded research regarding the health-related aspects of smoking. Research funded by the tobacco industry can, therefore, never include claims, recommendations, links or conclusions regarding electronic nicotine delivery devices, nicotine use or other tobacco-related products” [71].

3.4 Recent collaborations between Dutch academic institutions and the tobacco industry

Despite widespread opposition to collaborating with the tobacco industry and statements from universities deeming such collaborations unacceptable², our findings show that Dutch academic ties with the industry have persisted in recent years (Table 1). Over the past 20 years, there have been instances of funded research, academics holding additional roles at tobacco companies, master’s theses supervised by industry representatives, and sponsorship of student associations. We identified staff members with dual affiliations and industry-linked research publications as recently as 2024.

Besides direct collaborations with tobacco producers, researchers are, sometimes unknowingly, linked to the tobacco industry via health-tech companies. Investments in the pharmaceutical and health markets is part of the strategy of the tobacco industry to secure its business model via diversification. The industry funds research on smoking-related disorders, drugs, therapies, and cessation aids for individuals struggling with addiction or illnesses caused by smoking [18]. These indirect funding structures often leave scientists, universities, and journals unaware of the tobacco industry’s involvement in research. *Follow the Money* writes that the line between the pharmaceutical and tobacco industries is blurring. As a result, it is sometimes difficult for scientists to escape the influence of cigarette manufacturers [18].

¹ Nevertheless, their study was still published in the European Respiratory Society (ERS) journal which said the research was not in breach of its policy as the grant from Vectura was initiated in 2018 [68].

² Examples are Utrecht [4] and Maastricht [71].

For example, through pharmaceutical or health ventures, the tobacco industry gains channels to lobby policymakers and civil servants at conferences – which the tobacco industry is supposed to be barred from via the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control [18, 47]. A striking example of leveraging academic research for lobbying purposes is Philip Morris' intentional framing of a research question to associate cigarette smuggling with terrorism in 2018. This narrative was subsequently employed to lobby for stricter controls on cigarette smuggling, allegedly driven largely by the industry's concern over the negative impact of smuggling on its business interests. A researcher from Leiden University who worked on the project, looking back, found it a *"curious project"* and later understood that the *"strange question"* about the relation between cigarette smuggling and terrorism was inserted in the research by the funder Philip Morris [72].

Table 1: Non-exhaustive overview of Dutch academic ties to the tobacco industry from 2005 to date (2025)

Type	Examples
Academics with additional (advisory) roles in tobacco industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arkadiusz Kuczaj has been a manager R&D at Philip Morris International (PMI) since 2009, focusing on aerosol research, and from 2013 was also an associate professor at the University of Twente (UT) [73, 74], stopping in September 2024 (according to his LinkedIn). His affiliation is, however, given as both PMI and UT at a conference in October 2024 [75]. He published papers, specifically on e-cigarettes between 2016 and 2024 [76, 77, 78, 79]. He filed patents relating to vaping, most recently in 2024 [80]. According to the ERCOFTAC website, he is in a "special interest group" with Prof. Bernard J. Geurts from UT [81]. • Erik Lutjens, a professor of pension law at VU Amsterdam, currently serves as a lawyer at DLA Piper, a firm that has represented the tobacco industry in legal cases, and chairs the legal advisory committee of the British American Tobacco (BAT) pension fund [82]. • Irene Asscher-Vonk, served as a commissioner at Philip Morris Holland, while she was also a professor at the Radboud University (2002-2009) [83]. • Rinus van Schendelen (Erasmus University, EUR) served as an advisor to the tobacco industry between 2003 until at least 2014. His involvement was not always disclosed, and he financed his research through funding from the tobacco industry. The nature of his advisory role and funding was not always transparent, leading to significant controversy over his links to the tobacco sector, especially when conflicts of interest were questioned during his public engagements [84, 85]. • A researcher from Amsterdam Medical Center (affiliated with Universiteit van Amsterdam and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam) declares "Grant/Research support" from or for Japan Tobacco International (JTI) in papers published in 2012 [86] and 2013 [87, 88]. However, this is not declared in another paper published in 2013 [89].

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Type	Examples
Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Philip Morris International founded PMI Impact in 2016, a foundation focused on funding research into cigarette smuggling and the associated criminal activities [90]. Since its inception, the initiative has supported universities around the world, now entering its third round of funding. Leiden University participated in a study conducted by the Slovakian think tank Globsec, “Who are the European jihadis”, published in 2018 [91], which had received funding from PMI, thereby indirectly benefiting from this financial support [72, 92]. ● Utrecht University also received funding from PMI Impact in 2017-2018 for research on cigarette smuggling. Following public pressure, the university chose to return the funding and independently finance the research [12, 13]. ● Researchers at EUR suddenly and unwillingly found themselves affiliated with PMI, when PMI acquired Vectura in 2021. They had signed a 4-year agreement with Vectura in 2018, which consisted of an unconditional research grant for a PhD trajectory on the structure and function of small airways in patients with severe asthma [71]. While the acquisition of Vectura by PMI brought the researchers “deep moral concern”, one of the researchers finished his PhD [93] and his study was published in the European Respiratory Society (ERS) journal which said the research was not in breach of its policy as the grant from Vectura was initiated in 2018 [68]. ● The <i>Nederlandse Organisatie voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek</i> (TNO, Dutch Organisation for Applied Scientific Research) received funding from BAT for a 2006 study into building ventilation [94]. Lobbying for ventilation as harm reduction from passive smoke was part of the industry’s strategy to push back on restrictions on smoking indoors [32]. <p>UT & Philip Morris:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Philip Morris funded two PhD-students at the UT between 2008-2012 for the project ‘Simulation of heat and mass transport processes’ [95]. ● Philip Morris Products S.A. funded the UT PhD research project ‘Multi-scale modeling and simulations of aerosol nucleation and transport in porous media’, finalised in 2016 (Prof. Bernard Geurts was the UT supervisor, Arkadiusz Kuczaj represented PMI) [96, 97]. ● Philip Morris Products S.A. funded the UT Postdoc research project ‘Numerical methods for porous media flows with non-equilibrium heat transfer’, 2013-2015 (Prof. Bernard Geurts was the UT supervisor) [98, 99]. ● Philip Morris Products S.A. funded PhD research at UT which was published in 2012 with the title ‘Simulating microtransport in realistic porous media’ (Prof. Bernard Geurts was the UT supervisor). The research ‘is an important step in understanding the physics of smoking’ and researched whether lower temperature could reduce the release of harmful substances from cigarettes [100].

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Type	Examples
<p>Research collaboration or co-publication with tobacco companies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bernard J. Geurts, professor at UT and part-time professor at TU Eindhoven (TU/e), supervised several PhD and Postdoc projects funded by Philip Morris [97, 98, 100], co-published several papers with colleague and PMI employee Arkadiusz K. Kuczaj on aerosol formation, for example in 2014 and 2017 [101, 102], is in a “special interest group” with him [81], and provided input and developed the aerosol model and algorithm used in a study by Kuczaj and another PMI employee on e-cigarettes in 2016 [76]. • Researchers from Wageningen University and Leiden University co-published a paper in 2014 on bioactive compounds with pharmaceutical properties with an employee of Philip Morris Products S.A. [103], although the latter was a postdoc at the University of Zurich at the time the research was carried out [104]. • A researcher from Leiden University co-published a paper in 2020 on an alternative approach to lab animals in pharmaceutical drug development and academic research with an employee of Philip Morris International R&D [105]. • A researcher from TU/e and Prof. Geurts from UT co-published with Philip Morris employees including Arkadiusz Kuczaj in 2012, title: ‘Fully-developed conjugate heat transfer in porous media with uniform heating’ [106]. • Some medical papers have large author counts. For example, in one 2021 paper with 77 authors [107], a researcher from JTI is listed together with five from Erasmus University Medical centre. In some cases work by separate teams contributes towards a large paper. This appears to be the case in a 2022 Nature paper with over 200 authors [108], where the same JTI researcher appears alongside authors from several Dutch university medical centres. • An academic from Open Universiteit co-authored a paper on “Action Learning” with co-authors at BAT Niemeyer, around a case study at that factory [109].
<p>Internship and master theses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Philip Morris is mentioned as hosting MSc students from Computer Science, University of Twente, between 2003-2005 [110]. • Philip Morris Holland B.V. supervised ‘A study towards yield optimization for the Expanded Tobacco II process of Philip Morris Holland B.V’ from a master student at TU Delft in 2014. The thesis was confidential until 2019 [111]. • Master thesis assignment from Philip Morris Holland B.V. about investment policy of IT activities, Open Universiteit, 2008 [112]. • Master thesis with Philip Morris Holland B.V. ‘Incremental process innovations in a mature industry. exploring the factors of influence on implementation success’, TU/e, 2006 [113]. • Master thesis with BAT Niemeyer at University of Groningen in 2011. From the abstract: “BAT Niemeyer is taking steps to implement the procedure described in this thesis” [114]. • A thesis in 2018 at the Open Universiteit about ‘The influence of organizational culture on IT Governance maturity’ has interviews with employees at BAT but does not appear to be commissioned by BAT [115].
<p>Sponsoring of student associations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JTI paid student associations to have the exclusive right to sell their cigarettes at the associations’ clubhouses. Nine student associations across the Netherlands signed contracts with JTI. In exchange for selling only JTI products in the cigarette vending machines at their clubhouses, the associations received sponsorship money. The exact amounts involved are unknown, as the agreements include a confidentiality clause. JTI was fined for violating tobacco advertising regulations in 2018 [116, 117].

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

Type	Examples
(Medical) research collaborations with health-tech companies	<p>Journalists from <i>The Investigative Desk</i> and <i>The British Medical Journal</i> identified 876 medical and scientific studies of the past 20 years involving one or more researchers who received some form of funding from a tobacco manufacturer [68]. Their database lists multiple connections between Dutch academics and the tobacco industry, mediated through investments in biotech and health-tech companies:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conflicts of interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Professor of Brain Stimulation and Applied Cognitive Neuroscience at Maastricht University serves as the chief science advisor for PlatoScience, which is approximately 20–25% owned by BAT [118, 119]. PlatoScience provides a headset which “has been found to be effective in reducing symptoms of depression, addiction cravings, and pains” [120]. The UM professor has also published together with PlatoScience employees in 2022 and 2023 [121, 122]. • Researchers at Erasmus MC’s Department of Dermatology received an (unrestricted) research grant from Micreos, a Dutch biotechnology company specialising in endolysin-based antibacterial therapies which is partially owned by Altria. Between 2017 and 2021, this research grant resulted in the publication of research papers focusing on skin conditions such as atopic dermatitis [123, 124, 125, 126, 127, 128, 129]. Active and passive exposure to smoke are associated with increased atopic dermatitis prevalence [130]. • A cardiologist affiliated with the University of Groningen [131] held an additional role with Biofourmis. The database of The Investigative Desk and BMI lists 15 papers published between 2020-2024, see for example the most recent two [132, 133]. Biofourmis is a health-tech company partially owned by Philip Morris International (PMI) [134]. 2. Research collaborations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biognosys, a Swiss proteomics firm partially owned by PMI, has collaborated on research with a professor of human nutrition from Maastricht University Medical Centre, published in 2019. The title is ‘Analysis of 1508 Plasma Samples by Capillary-Flow Data-Independent Acquisition Profiles Proteomics of Weight Loss and Maintenance’ [135]. • A 2020 study on fecal microbiota differences among domesticated equine species includes an author who previously worked with Wageningen University, but at the time of publishing was affiliated with Micreos, a company partially owned by Altria. The other authors are researchers from Utrecht University and Wageningen University & Research [136].
Scientific conferences	<p>The tobacco industry has been using participation in and sponsorship of scientific conferences, symposia, and workshops as a strategy to normalise its presence in the academic world since the 1950s [137]. A study shows that between 2012 and 2021, representatives from PMI and BAT attended 213 scientific events, primarily in the fields of toxicology, medicine, biology, and chemistry [138]. 40% of those events were in the European region. While the exact locations of these events were not published in the article, the global nature of the scientific community means that researchers and doctors frequently attend international conferences.</p> <p>Other publications show that Dutch scientists were present at events together with PMI in 2010 and 2012 [139, 140], with JTI in 2018 and 2022 [141, 142], as well as its “philanthropic” foundation, JTI Foundation in 2019 [143].</p>

3.5 Factors behind shifting attitudes towards tobacco industry collaborations

Our initial thesis was that social change on critical issues, especially those grounded in scientific evidence, often originates within universities and academia. We expected universities to be frontrunners in both word and deed, leading the charge in tobacco control efforts. However, our research revealed the opposite: Dutch universities have largely lagged behind in formally addressing collaborations with the tobacco industry and have tended to follow, rather than lead, tobacco control initiatives. While Dutch universities largely failed to take the lead in restricting tobacco industry collaborations, other parts of the academic ecosystem — namely medical journals and cancer research funders — have implemented policies that

set de facto boundaries. In addition, the attitude towards such collaborations shifted over time. Our findings suggest that shifting relationships between Dutch academia and the tobacco industry was driven by several factors: a change in public opinion as a result of stricter tobacco control, growing awareness of the obstructive practices of the industry, opposition from professional associations, changes in funding policies, and restrictions on publishing industry-funded research. International developments have also played a role in shaping attitudes within the Dutch academic community.

International shifting attitudes

In the US and the UK, attitudes were shifting on accepting medical research funding from the tobacco industry as early as 1996 [144], although tobacco funding was still mainstream: Cambridge University let British American Tobacco fund a professorship that same year for GBP1.5M (approximately GBP3.6M in today's terms) [145]. Cancer research foundations including Cancer Research UK, the Norwegian Cancer Society, and members of the Union Internationale Contre le Cancer stopped funding research in research institutions accepting tobacco funding in the late 1990s [29]. Cancer Research UK stated that it would “not provide financial support where those who are, or would be, supported by Cancer Research UK funds are working in such proximity to others supported by tobacco industry funding that there is any possibility or likelihood that facilities, equipment or other resources will be shared” [65].

In the Netherlands, the attitude shift on tobacco collaborations appeared to happen later, in the 2000s and 2010s.

Change in public opinion due to tobacco control policies

Willemsen notes how, in Dutch politics, tobacco use shifted from being perceived as an economic benefit to a public health threat between the 1960s and now. The years 2002-2004 were decisive, “when the Tobacco Act was amended and Minister Borst successfully took tobacco policy out of the sphere of influence of the trade ministry and under the control of the Ministry of Health, resulting in tobacco control measures that had a huge impact on society” [32].

These policy changes not only reshaped governmental priorities but also played a crucial role in shifting public attitudes toward tobacco use. Stricter regulations, combined with growing awareness of health risks, contributed to a societal shift in which tobacco consumption became increasingly viewed as a public health concern rather than a personal choice or economic asset. For example, support among smokers for smoke-free workplaces rose from 56% to 79% in a year [32].

This example shows that taking (policy) action itself can drive attitudinal change. However, without formalised policies and mechanisms to monitor both direct and indirect collaborations, shifts in public opinion may not lead to lasting institutional change.

Growing awareness of the misleading and obstructive practices of the tobacco industry

In the 2010s, reports from Marc Willemsen, health advocates and investigative journalism shed light on how the industry had historically worked to delay or weaken Dutch tobacco control efforts. The campaign *Rookpreventie Jeugd* [51] (Youth Smoking Prevention) by Wanda de Kanter and Paulien Dekker, along with the formation of the *Alliantie Nederland Rookvrij* (Netherlands Smoke-Free Alliance) in 2018, framed tobacco control as an issue of protecting youth and achieving a Smoke-Free Generation [146]. These initiatives raised public awareness about how the industry strategically targets young people, obstructs policymaking, and misleads the public about the harms of smoking. The 2016 ‘Sick of Smoking’ lawsuit, in which lawyer Bénédicte Ficq attempted to prosecute tobacco companies for intentionally addicting consumers, further intensified public scrutiny [147].

In 2017, public backlash against an announced collaboration between Utrecht University and PMI was significant, prompting the university to reconsider its position [12, 13]. This strong backlash and media attention marked a turning point, reinforcing the norm that academic institutions should not engage with the tobacco industry. In 2018, Leiden University faced scrutiny for participating in a study that received indirect funding from Philip Morris—something the university was reportedly unaware of at the time [92].

Ethical concerns and actions by health professionals

In the US, in 2017, organisations like the American Cancer Society [148] and the World Heart Federation [149] spoke out against tobacco collaborations. In the Netherlands, profession-

als were less vocal than in the US and the UK (see Section 2). One Dutch organisation stands out: in 2013, the Nederlandse Vereniging voor Oncologie (NVvO) expressed ethical concerns regarding partnerships between healthcare institutions and the tobacco industry. They addressed these concerns in a letter to Yvonne van Rooy, the chair of the Nederlandse Vereniging van Ziekenhuizen (NVZ), urging the NVZ to publicly support tobacco discouragement policies and to actively promote such policies within Dutch hospitals. This action was prompted by an article in *Vrij Nederland*, which highlighted that the employers' organization VNO-NCW was lobbying against anti-smoking measures at both the national and European levels [150].

Researchers at Erasmus University who were receiving funding from Vectura describe how international health associations condemned PMI's takeover of Vectura in 2021 and called for boycotts. In January 2022, the Forum of International Respiratory Societies reiterated that its members could not engage with companies owned by tobacco firms, in line with their ethical codes [71].

Tighter policies by cancer research funders

KWF (Dutch Cancer Society), a major funder of cancer research in the Netherlands, tightened its guidelines in response to the controversy surrounding Utrecht University's collaboration with the tobacco industry [4]. KWF had long maintained policies against tobacco industry ties, but in 2017, it expanded these restrictions. Under the new rules, not only are principal investigators prohibited from working with the tobacco industry, but this restriction now applies to all project participants. These stricter guidelines had significant implications for universities that rely heavily on KWF funding, effectively forcing many institutions to reassess their industry partnerships.

A KWF spokesperson explained in 2018: *"We do not consider the tobacco industry to be a normal commercial business, the impact of smoking on health is enormous. One in two smokers is at risk of developing a disease. In the Netherlands, 20,000 people die each year as a result of their addiction, 12,000 of whom from lung cancer. In our view, you should not want to collaborate with such companies"* [4].

Journals restricting tobacco industry influence

Already in 1996, the American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine, the American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology and the Journal of Health Psychology stopped publishing tobacco-industry funded work to address the overwhelming evidence of the tobacco industry's scientific misconduct [151].

Despite arguing against such a ban at the time [152], in 2013, The British Medical Journal (BMJ) implemented a policy to no longer publish studies funded wholly or partially by the tobacco industry [153]. Since 2024, they also exclude work where the authors have personal financial ties with the tobacco industry. While most leading medical journals don't have such policies in place [154], the policy of BMJ and seven other medical journals made it more challenging for tobacco-funded research to be published, reducing the incentive for researchers and institutions to collaborate with the industry.

We also speculate that the existence of so called "industry-captured journals" - journals with editors in or sympathetic to the tobacco industry publishing highly skewed research - such as Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology [155] may have been another reason for journals to distance themselves from tobacco influence.

4 KEY PARALLELS AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE TOBACCO AND FOSSIL FUEL INDUSTRY

The business strategy, use of and influence on research, and PR tactics of the tobacco and fossil fuel industries show many similarities, presented in Section 4.1 and Table 2. However, there are also notable differences between the industries, which are outlined in Section 4.2 and shown in Table 3.

4.1 Key parallels between the tobacco and fossil fuel industry

The tobacco industry provides the most well-documented example of commercially-driven misinformation and agenda-setting. Since the 1950s, the tobacco industry has strategically

used scientific collaborations to manipulate research and cast doubt on the health risks of smoking and passive smoke [156]. By creating an atmosphere of uncertainty, the tobacco industry was able to continue promoting its products despite the growing evidence of the harmful effects of tobacco use [157, 158]. Similar strategies of delay are observed in the fossil fuel industry as well: shifting blame onto the consumer, denying scientific consensus, and strategically publishing industry-funded science [159, 160]. Both industries rely on 'harm reduction' strategies, such as promoting vaping as a safer alternative to smoking [161] and positioning gas [162] and blue hydrogen [163] as low-carbon or transition fuels. They also use 'harm avoidance' tactics, like advocating for ventilation measures in smoking areas [32] and promoting carbon capture and storage (CCS) as a climate solution [164].

Both industries have been actively involved in casting doubt on scientific consensus, often through the use of so-called "alternative causation" arguments. The book *Merchants of Doubt* [157] describes how the same industry-favourable scientists that spread doubt around the dangers of smoking, also disseminated false information on the causes of climate change. Industry involvement may shape research results as well; a meta-study of research into natural gas found that research funded by the fossil fuel industry was more favourable towards natural gas [165].

In addition to direct influence on research outcomes, academic collaboration provides industries with the ability to shape research directions and gain legitimacy within the academic world, policymaking, and the broader public [158, 159]. 'Acquiring respectability by association' was a tactic used by the tobacco industry in the late 1990s [166]. In documents received by the Dutch Mapping Fossil Ties Coalition in response to a Freedom of Information (FOI) request, universities are quite frank about this towards the fossil fuel industry: Leiden University proposed to Aramco in 2014 that a collaboration would provide them "access to excellent students and alumni for internships and vacancies" and "the opportunity to be connected to ... the reputation of Leiden University" [167]. The university of Maastricht asked Aramco in 2017 to choose which research proposal to fund out of a choice of four, each of which "links in with Saudi Aramco's business interests" and offers to "further discuss the ample PR and marketing opportunities, outreach possibilities and other benefits that will support and enhance Aramco's regional and national profile" [168].

Furthermore, contracts for collaboration with the fossil fuel industry often have clauses allowing redaction of results or delaying publication.³ While this may be useful for protecting proprietary information, such constructions have been misused by the tobacco industry to bury unwanted results [156].

Table 2: Key parallels between the tobacco and fossil fuel industry

Aspect	Tobacco Industry	Fossil Fuel Industry
Core product impacts health and environment	Product causes widespread health issues, including cancer and respiratory diseases. Tobacco products are the most littered item on the planet, and the industry's carbon footprint is equivalent to one-fifth of the CO ₂ produced by the commercial airline industry, according to the WHO [169].	Product a leading cause of global warming, air pollution, and associated health impacts [170].
Use of doubt as strategy	Promotes doubt about the health risks of smoking to delay regulation [158].	Promotes doubt about the causes and extent of climate change to delay action [158].
Research: alternative causation	Funds research to misrepresent smoking risks and create conflicting results [158].	Funds research to downplay the role of fossil fuels in climate change [158].
Research: recruitment of experts	Enlists doctors and public figures to downplay risks and challenge regulations [171].	Enlists scientists and public figures to question climate science [172], downplay risks and challenge regulations [173].
Public relations: diversify into alternatives	Invests in pharmaceuticals and health products to appear socially responsible [174].	Promotes efforts in renewable energy and carbon capture, without challenging core business, to enhance public image (greenwashing) [175].

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³ These will be published in a forthcoming report from Mapping Fossil Ties Coalition, but collaboration clauses can already be viewed in the results of the freedom of information requests, see: <https://www.mappingfossilies.org/Results.html>

Table 2 – continued from previous page

Aspect	Tobacco Industry	Fossil Fuel Industry
Public relations: individualism	Frames smoking as a personal choice and markets “safer” products (e.g., e-cigarettes) [160].	Frames fossil fuel use as a personal choice, e.g. “carbon footprint” and onus on individual to stop demanding fossil products [160].
Advocacy: harm reduction strategy	Promotion of “light” products [176] and promotion of e-cigarettes/vaping [161].	Promotion of gas [162] and blue hydrogen [163] as low-carbon or transition fuels.
Advocacy: harm avoidance strategy	Promotion and political support for ventilation measures and innovative air systems [32].	Promotion and political support for carbon capture and storage [164].
Advocacy: legal and political lobbying	Engages in extensive lobbying on a national and international level to weaken or block regulations [177, 32] based on arguments of economics and individual choice (see Section 2).	Engages in extensive lobbying on a national and international level to delay climate policies and promote industry-friendly legislation [178], based on arguments of economics and energy security [179].
Advocacy: front groups and “astroturfing”⁴	Establishes advocacy organisations to present industry interests as independent views [181] [32].	Establishes advocacy organisations [182, 183] and uses think tanks and NGOs to advocate for policies favouring the industry [184].
Regulatory evasion	Exploits loopholes in advertising bans and other regulations [185].	Exploits regulatory gaps to continue emissions-intensive activities [186].
Global influence	Operates across borders to benefit from weaker regulatory systems in different countries [187].	Targets less regulated markets for fossil fuel expansion [186].
Promotion to youth and at universities	Organised fun events and challenges for children in the late 1990’s, product placement in cartoons, promoted itself at universities by e.g. sponsoring student societies and events [117, 54] and employed marketing strategies targeted at children or to which they are susceptible [188].	Organises children’s festivals e.g. “Generation Discover” [189], promotes itself at universities by e.g. sponsoring student societies and events [19].

4.2 Key differences between the tobacco and fossil fuel industry

Despite the many similarities, there are differences between the two industries. Firstly, the production and consumption of tobacco products can be eliminated rapidly without major consequences. The health risks associated with smoking are well known, and society has already made significant strides in reducing smoking rate. ‘Only’ 19% of the Dutch adult population smoked in 2023. On the other hand, fossil fuels are embedded deeply in nearly every sector of the global economy—energy production, transportation, agriculture, manufacturing, and the chemicals that go into everyday products. A change in policy that would lead to a rise in prices of either tobacco or fossil fuels would - in 2025 - affect more people in the case of fossil fuels, most significantly in the form of rising prices of energy or petrol.

Economic aspects of phasing out industry and structural dependence

The tobacco industry currently plays a much smaller role within the Dutch economy than the fossil fuel industry. In previous years, however, the situation was different. According to the “*Voorlichtingsbureau Sigaretten en Shag*” (Information Bureau for Cigarettes and Rolling Tobacco), the Dutch tobacco industry in 1985 was in absolute terms the largest contributor to the national trade balance, with an export surplus of over f1.2bn (ECU 500 million), and production was growing year on year [190]. Even in 1999, the tobacco industry achieved a percentage growth in turnover that was clearly above the average growth for the total Dutch industry, and accounted for over a quarter of tobacco production within the EU [191]. In the Netherlands, the tobacco industry included 27 companies in 1998, which employed

⁴ Astroturfing is organized activity that is intended to create a false impression of a widespread, spontaneously arising, grassroots movement in support of or in opposition to something (such as a political policy) but that is in reality initiated and controlled by a concealed group or organization (such as a corporation) [180].

about 5,500 people at the time [191] - down from over 30,000 people in tobacco production (excluding distribution) in 1939, and currently less than 1000.

The number of people employed directly in the extraction of crude oil and gas was 3,200 in 2022, however, industries heavily dependant on fossil oil and gas employed many more, such as refining (5,200), basic chemical production (30,900) and plastics production (41,300), to name only a few [192]. On top of this there are industries and businesses involved in supplying the materials, infrastructure and services to heavy industry. Scaling down the fossil fuel sector could yield substantial health benefits by reducing pollution and associated diseases. However, to avoid economic drawbacks, it is crucial to implement strategies that promote sustainable industries and support workers transitioning from fossil fuel-dependent roles.

Thus, while both industries have a history of employing similar strategies to protect their interests, the structural dependency on fossil fuels makes it a far more complex issue that demands careful planning to address. This allows the fossil fuel industry to frame fossil fuels as pragmatic solutions or geopolitically important [193], and claim that their knowledge and expertise “can contribute to the switch to clean energy” and that collaboration with universities is “indispensable” for this [194, 195]. The argument that collaborations with the fossil fuel industry are essential due to their financial resources, knowledge, and expertise is frequently raised in discussions within academic institutions [196, 197].

Evaluating conflicts of interest

There is broad recognition that collaborations with the tobacco industry present significant conflicts of interest — reflected in Principle 1 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC), which states that “*There is a fundamental and irreconcilable conflict between the tobacco industry’s interests and public health policy interests*” [42].

Unlike with tobacco-funded research, there are very few journals that restrict publication of fossil fuel-funded papers. To our knowledge, only the *BMJ* has a policy explicitly prohibiting the publication of research tied to the fossil fuel industry [198]. Dutch universities justify collaboration with the fossil fuel industry on energy transition and sustainability projects. Yet, as a Dutch public health authority director noted as early as 1996, the tobacco industry funds research to influence debates and researchers, not out of philanthropy. “*The suggestion that researchers are immune to such influences is a noble but highly unrealistic thesis*” [151]. This also applies to the fossil fuel industry.

Despite clear parallels, the potential for conflict of interest in fossil fuel collaborations remains largely unacknowledged by most universities and researchers. Nearly all Dutch universities claim they only engage with the fossil fuel companies on projects contributing to the energy transition [11]. However, this overlooks the inherent conflict of interest posed by oil and gas companies whose core business is fundamentally at odds with long-term climate goals [199].

For instance, Utrecht University’s draft ‘Integral Assessment Framework for Research’ requires Executive Board approval for partnerships with the tobacco or arms industries, and notes such approval is highly unlikely. In contrast, fossil fuel collaborations fall under a separate, more permissive framework that allows for significant exceptions [25].

Awareness of industry tactics

A further notable difference between the two industries is the broad recognition of the misleading practices of the tobacco industry and their harmful lobbying practices, as addressed in Article 5.3 of the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC): “*the tobacco industry has operated for years with the express intention of subverting the role of governments and of WHO in implementing public health policies to combat the tobacco epidemic*” [42]. On the other hand, obstruction by the fossil fuel industry receives less attention, and representatives of the fossil fuel industry are openly invited to shape climate policy (for example at the ‘climate tables’ that informed the Dutch climate accord [200]) and research agendas (for example in the ‘Topsectoren’ - public-private research and innovation programs⁵).

The study of tobacco control and tactics is an established academic field with specific journals such as *BMJ’s Tobacco Control* [202] and research groups such as the Tobacco Control

⁵ “*The Topsector policy was introduced to make up for the alleged downside of the system of centrally allocated subsidies. First, the investments in R&D were decentralised to give businesses and research institutes more voice in the determination of research projects and collaborations. Although the government remained involved, private partners would be in the lead in terms of seeking state support for their research- and innovation-related initiatives.*” [201]

Research Group at the University of Bath [203]. The obstructive tactics of the fossil fuel industry are studied in the emerging academic field of climate obstruction. The Climate Social Science Network (CSSN) wrote in 2021: “Scholars are just beginning to unearth the complex and highly developed network of organizations built to block action on the life-threatening issue of climate change” [204]. Despite efforts of researchers, progress on understanding and overcoming climate obstruction has been slow [205].

Table 3: Key differences between the tobacco and fossil fuel industry (in the Netherlands)

Aspect	Tobacco Industry	Fossil Fuel Industry
Economic impact of phase-out	As production moved abroad, the contribution to the national trade balance declined and consequently its national economic importance [32].	Deeply embedded in all sectors; scaling down requires careful planning to avoid economic disruptions.
Employment	Following the closures of British American Tobacco’s and Philip Morris’ factories, the importance of tobacco employment is seen by the government as negligible [32].	Direct employment in oil & gas (3,200 in 2022); many more in refining (5,200), basic chemicals (30,900), plastics (41,300) [192].
Policy influence	Banned from lobbying (although imperfect implementation of WHO FCTC leads to ongoing involvement [47]).	Industry still involved in policy discussions (e.g., “climate tables” [200], “Top-sector” research [201]).
Public perception	No longer seen as essential or beneficial to society, nor as a trustworthy partner.	The Dutch <i>poldermodel</i> (consensus decision making) and framing by the fossil fuel industry promote the view to decision-makers and the public that the fossil fuel sector must be involved in the energy transition [206].
Conflict of interest perception	Academic and medical collaboration is seen as a clear conflict of interest [42].	Academic collaboration on energy transition projects is generally not (yet) considered a conflict of interest [11].
Research & tactics study	Well-established field (e.g., BMJ’s Tobacco Control journal [202]).	Field of climate obstruction is emerging [207].

5 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNIVERSITY ENGAGEMENT WITH INDUSTRY

As Dutch universities currently work to establish guidelines for external partnerships, we present key insights from our brief research into tobacco industry and academic collaborations. We propose considerations for universities in navigating relationships with both the tobacco and fossil fuel industries which aim to help shape responsible engagement and safeguard academic integrity. Given the profound impact of both industries on public health—through tobacco-related diseases, air pollution and the health consequences of climate change—universities, researchers, research funders, journals, and medical professionals have a crucial role in promoting a healthier society by aligning research collaborations with public health and sustainability goals.

- 1) Dutch universities did not play a leading role in the shifting public opinion on tobacco, but rather followed the shifting public opinion, which was partly influenced by professional health/medical and societal organisations, and changes in funding policies by medical research funders.

Recommendation: Universities can consider whether they want to take a more leading role in public opinion-forming around the tobacco and the fossil fuel industry. For universities that have researchers working on tobacco control, climate obstruction and public health, this could be considered valorisation of their research. Universities might consider creating space for debate, including critical societal voices and voices from health organisations, as well as those familiar with the industry, but without the industry itself.⁶

- 2) Medical journals and cancer research funders played a key role internationally in discouraging tobacco ties by rejecting industry-linked research.

⁶ If the industry is present, it is crucial that discussions are facilitated carefully to ensure a balanced, transparent, and fact-checked exchange of ideas, avoiding undue influence and ensuring that the focus remains on public health and research integrity.

Recommendation: Researchers, health organisations and campaigners in favour of restricting academic collaborations with fossil fuel industry might engage with medical, climate and environment-focused journals to request a funding and publication policy around fossil fuel collaborations.

- 3) Health professionals and academic institutions in the Netherlands have historically had a weaker voice in countering industry lobbying, especially compared to countries like the UK where the response has been more vocal.

Recommendation: Professional organisations (*'beroepsverenigingen'*) and academics who seek to strengthen public health efforts could consider speaking out against undue industry influence. By doing so, they would help amplify the voices of others calling for reduced power and influence from harmful industries.

- 4) Dutch universities do not have policies in place that restrict collaboration with the tobacco industry, but despite this, the Dutch academic community and administration generally agree that it is 'not done' to collaborate with the tobacco industry.

Recommendation: Dutch academic institutions should consider incorporating the tobacco industry into current policy frameworks surrounding external collaborations, ensuring a clear and consistent approach, and solidifying this stance towards the tobacco industry within official policy.

- 5) Support for a policy may grow after implementing it: support for a smoking ban increased and attitudes changed after the ban on smoking indoors was implemented, and similarly, at the VU Amsterdam, attitudes shifted after cutting research ties to the fossil fuel industry.⁷

Recommendation: Universities should consider implementing policies that safeguard academic integrity and uphold university values, even when there is no consensus (yet) within the academic community. Clear rationale and open debates around such policies can foster constructive dialogue, promote transparency, and encourage broader support.

- 6) Policies restricting tobacco industry collaboration may not fully prevent partnerships due to indirect funding structures. Universities and academic journals unknowingly maintain ties to the tobacco industry through subsidiaries or companies that appear to be focused on health, but are (partially) funded or owned by the tobacco industry.

Recommendation: When developing partnership guidelines, it is crucial to consistently review definitions and incorporate subsidiaries and indirect ties. Researchers and academic staff can investigate potential tobacco or fossil fuel ownership through sources like annual reports, press releases, and company databases to ensure transparency and avoid hidden connections [68].

- 7) The Dutch academic community and administration are insufficiently aware of current academic collaborations and affiliations with the tobacco industry. While universities publish external funding of professors and ancillary activities of staff, they do not provide transparency on research collaboration and funding.

Recommendation: Universities should provide more transparency on industry collaborations (tobacco, fossil fuel and other industries).

- 8) The tobacco and fossil fuel industries are among the most harmful to public health and have historically employed similar tactics to protect their interests. While the WHO and many academics acknowledge that there is "*a fundamental and irreconcilable conflict between the tobacco industry's interests and public health policy interests*", Dutch universities

⁷ After the VU Amsterdam banned research partnerships with fossil fuel partners, initially hesitant staff members—some of whom had actively opposed the decision—later expressed support and pride in the university's leadership. This shift was attributed both to clearer messaging over time and the human tendency to align with an established status quo. WHO guidelines on collaborations with the tobacco industry were also referenced by staff in arguments urging the VU to take a similar stance on fossil fuel partnerships—a strategy that proved effective, as key stakeholders later acknowledged it had a significant impact on their thinking [30]. Further, the action taken by universities as a result of pressure from a relatively small group of students and staff precipitated university-wide discussions where the community was forced to engage with the issue. A survey at TU Delft, in which approximately 10% of the academic community participated, found that 87% of respondents had never previously expressed views on fossil fuel collaborations. Despite the university's strong ties to the fossil fuel industry, only 17% of respondents recommended against taking measures to limit collaboration[31]. These examples show that taking (policy) action itself can drive attitudinal change.

justify working with the fossil fuel industry if it is on projects related to the energy transition.

Recommendation: Dutch universities should recognise the conflict of interest between the fossil fuel industry and independent climate transition research. Professional organisations and academics who seek to strengthen public health efforts could advocate for consistency in how industries with harmful public health and environmental impacts are treated in academia.

- 9) A key difference between the tobacco and fossil fuel industries is the complexity of phasing out fossil fuels from the global economy compared to eliminating tobacco use. This is, however, no justification for allowing the fossil fuel industry to shape research agendas, influence policy, or maintain research collaborations—especially given its clear conflict of interest in the energy transition.

Recommendation:

- a) Critically evaluate new research collaborations with the fossil fuel industry, particularly on energy transition and sustainability projects, to avoid conflicts of interest.
 - b) Phase out fossil fuel industry influence in research agenda-setting, research consortia, and public funding programs.
 - c) End ancillary roles of researchers and university board members that create conflicts of interest.
- 10) Some researchers and academic institutions do not fully recognise how industries leverage scientific research and academic affiliations to delay policy changes and shape public opinion. This is reflected in the limited awareness of indirect collaborations with the tobacco industry and the tendency to assess fossil fuel partnerships only at the project level. While tobacco industry tactics are well-documented, the study of climate obstruction remains an emerging and sometimes controversial field.

Recommendation: Universities should educate staff and students on the role of research and academic institutions in the broader economic landscape, as well as the tactics used by the tobacco and fossil fuel industries to deny the harm they cause, spread doubt, and delay regulation and accountability (see ‘tobacco tactics’ [203, 208] and ‘the disinformation playbook’ [209]). Integrating this into mandatory ethics training for researchers would help build awareness and safeguard academic integrity.

6 AVENUES FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Mapping and analysing tobacco industry ties of Dutch academia

Our brief study identified several recent and ongoing academic connections to the tobacco industry. Future research could provide a more comprehensive overview, examining the prevalence of these ties over time and identifying which universities have the strongest or weakest links. With universities currently shaping their policies on industry collaborations, it will be particularly important to monitor any new partnerships that may emerge.

Journal policies and industry involvement

Future research could explore which medical and academic journals have established policies regarding industry involvement, specifically with the fossil fuel industry. Additionally, investigating which journals publish the most papers co-authored with fossil fuel industry representatives could provide valuable insights into the extent of industry influence. Research could also examine the role of “industry-captured” journals—publications with editorial boards sympathetic to industry interests—and assess their influence on academic discourse. A focus on the specific policies these journals have in place to manage or disclose industry affiliations would be valuable in understanding the transparency and potential biases in published research.

Scholar engagement and collaboration

It would be valuable to connect with researchers in fields like cancer research, who once may have received funding from the tobacco industry but have seen attitudes shift away from such collaborations. Understanding the factors that contributed to these changing attitudes could provide valuable insights into how academic institutions can better navigate conflicts of interest and promote more ethical research practices moving forward.

Additionally, it would be valuable to engage with scholars working on the commercial determinants of health, particularly those examining the role of unhealthy commodity industries like tobacco and fossil fuels. Research could explore how these scholars view the influence of industries like fossil fuels within academic contexts, as well as existing collaborative efforts aimed at mitigating or confronting industry interference in public health research.

Attitudes and public discourse

Examining attitudes towards the tobacco and fossil fuel industries among students, faculty, and the general public offers insights into how these industries are perceived and how those perceptions influence the academic environment. Research could explore how exposure to specific information, social networks, and the implementation of institutional policies or guidelines shape these attitudes. This research would be crucial for understanding the broader social and cultural factors that influence academic decisions related to industry collaboration and could inform strategies to reduce industry influence in academic settings.

New trends in the tobacco industry

In recent years, the tobacco industry has increasingly focused on the development of new products, such as e-cigarettes, heated tobacco, and nicotine pouches. In contrast to tightening regulations surrounding cigarette sales and the growing global pressure to reduce the smoking of traditional cigarettes, e-cigarette regulation is still relatively permissive [45] and companies such as Philip Morris International have tried to use them to get around advertising laws [210].

At the same time, tobacco use among children is rising, and vaping is a large part of this rise: according to the RIVM the percentage of adolescents (12-16 years) who vape weekly has increased from 2% to 9% between 2019 and 2023 (conventional smoking increased from 4% to 6%) [211, 212]. Advertisements for vapes have been criticised for being targeted at children and youth [213], since marketing of e-cigarettes has been associated with increased use among youth [214]. In a survey of youth aged 16-19 in the US, Canada and England, over a third “perceived [vaping] ads as appealing and targeting non-smokers” and around 40% saw ads online [215].

Vaping and non-combustible tobacco products may be the new front in which public health and the tobacco industry clash. In Japan, Philip Morris International was found to have funded a researcher at the University of Tokyo to lobby for lower tax on its heated tobacco product IQOS [216], and funded research at Kyoto University [217] (independent research could not verify this). More research is recommended into this new business strategy and how academics might be involved in it.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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APPENDICES

Appendix A. Staff or board members of Dutch universities with additional roles with organisations in the fossil fuel industry in 2022-2024

Note: These tables are based on the Mapping Fossil Ties database, which itself is based on publicly available information from university and company websites, LinkedIn and freedom of information requests. It may not be complete and information may be outdated.[19]

Table 4: Externally-financed research chairs from a fossil fuel organisation in 2022-2025

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Financer	Description
TU Delft	Shell	Wim Mulder (Geophysical Imaging Methods) works at Shell and TU Delft. While both affiliations are still mentioned in a 2025 paper publication, his TUD profile page does not mention that he works at Shell. University website (webarchived) , Volkskrant article , Results of FOI request to TU Delft, published paper , University profile (webarchived) .
TU Delft	Shell	Ruud Henkes (Fluid flow): Full professor “Multiphase Flow in Pipelines” at the Department of Process & Energy, Faculty of Mechanical, Maritime, and Materials Engineering (3mE), 2018 – present: Principal Technical Expert Fluid Flow at Shell Projects & Technology (Process Engineering Discipline) in Amsterdam. University profile (webarchived) , Volkskrant article , Results of FOI request to TU Delft .
TU Delft	Shell	Cor van Kruijsdijk, a part-time professor at TU Delft, is paid by Shell and currently works on integrating renewables into energy systems. He previously spent nine years at Shell Research and became a professor at TU Delft in 1993. In 2005, he returned to Shell in Canada to work on heavy oil extraction but retained a ‘zero appointment’ at TU Delft to supervise PhD students. Shell later supported five endowed chairs at TU Delft, including van Kruijsdijk’s position in petroleum extraction. He is now part of the Electrical Sustainable Energy department within the Faculty of EWI. University website (webarchived) , University profile (webarchived) , LinkedIn (saved as PDF) , TU Delta article , University website article (webarchived) , Google Scholar profile (webarchived) , TU Delta article .
TU Delft	Shell	Prof. André van der Stap works 4 days a week at Shell as Principal Technical Expert in Offshore Structures and 1 day a week at TU Delft. University website (webarchived) .
TU Delft	Shell	Hadi Jamali-Rad is a principal AI scientist with Shell, also a part-time faculty (assistant professor) with the department of intelligent systems (INSY), the computer vision lab (CV Lab), at TU Delft. He has published work into monitoring integrity and production performance of oil and gas reservoirs. University website (webarchived) , Published paper with affiliation .

Continued on next page

Table 4 – continued from previous page

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Financer	Description
TU Delft	Energi Simulation	<p>Hadi Hajibeygi is Energi Simulation Chair holder of Sub-surface Storage and Multiscale Modeling at TUD. It is unclear if this is a sponsored professorship because it does not appear on TU Delft’s list. Founded in 1978, Energi Simulation (formerly Foundation CMG) “promotes and financially supports research and graduate students through research grants at universities”. According to their annual report, their ideology is that “Petroleum and Natural Gas will continue to contribute to global progress while technological advances will reduce their impact on the environment”. Energi Simulation’s members include several fossil fuel companies and of the 11 members of the board of directors, 10 have either work(ed), been board members, or holds an endowed chair of fossil fuel companies.</p> <p>Staff profile page, Energi Simulation Research report 2023-24, Externally financed chairs March 2024, Externally financed chairs March 2025, Energi Simulation Members, Energi Simulation Board of Directors,</p>
TU Delft	Energi Simulation	<p>Sebastian Geiger is Professor of Sustainable Geoenergy and Energi Simulation Chair at the Department of Geosciences, TUD. It is unclear if this is a sponsored professorship because it does not appear on TU Delft’s list. Initial documents about the Rapid Reservoir Modelling project on which he works suggests it can have dual use in oil and gas.</p> <p>Staff profile page, Energi Simulation Research report 2023-24, Externally financed chairs March 2024, Externally financed chairs March 2025, Energi Simulation Members, Energi Simulation Board of Directors, Paper about RRM suggesting dual use in oil and gas</p>
TU Delft	Equinor	<p>Prof A.W. Martinius is employed full-time at Equinor (since 2018) and has a 30% appointment at TU Delft (since 2016). He conducts research together with Equinor, gives lectures, and supervises PhD and Masters students. University website (webarchived), TU Delft staff directory (webarchived), Results of FOI request to TU Delft.</p>
TU Eindhoven	Shell	<p>Prof Rolf van Benthem is part-time professor of Coatings Technology at TU/e since 2002. He is currently employed by Shell as Chief Scientist (Materials Science & Engineering), where he started in 2022. He is also a member of the Materials Committee of NWO. University website (webarchived), Shell website (archived).</p>
TU Eindhoven	Shell	<p>Prof Thomas Weber is Principal Scientist at Shell Global Solutions, and part-time professor at the research group Inorganic Materials Chemistry of the Department of Chemical Engineering and Chemistry. University website (webarchived)</p>
TU Eindhoven	Shell	<p>Prof Michael Golombok is principal researcher in the new energies R&D department at Shell and part-time professor in the Power and Flow group in the department of mechanical engineering at TU/e. University website (webarchived).</p>
Universiteit Twente	Shell	<p>Prof. Dr. Ir. Arian Nijmeijer (Professor Inorganic Membranes at UT) also holds a full-time position at Shell Global Solutions International BV as Principal Science Expert Process Development. Opinion piece by Prof. Nijmeijer and Prof. Lange, University website (webarchived), ISPT website (webarchived), University overview of fossil fuel industry ties (webarchived).</p>

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Table 4 – continued from previous page

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Financer	Description
Universiteit Twente	Shell	<p>Professor Jean-Paul Lange was a full-time Principal Research Chemist at Shell Technology until 2024, with (unpaid) secondment to the UT for 1 day/week, effective since 2012. Jean-Paul Lange has worked for Shell since 1989. The position in the Sustainable Process Technology section has been held by the same person for more than 10 years. He is a lecturer in the Course "Sustainable Industrial Chemistry and Essential Skills". Opinion piece by Prof. Nijmeijer and Prof. Lange, University website (webarchived), Teaching catalogue of UTwente (webarchived), University faculty website (webarchived).</p>
VU Amsterdam	Shell	<p>Jan de Jager was an externally funded professor ("bijzondere leerstoel") at the VU - chair 'Regional and petroleum geology' sponsored by Shell. He was also a Professor Regional and Petroleum Geology at UU until 2015, while he was an oil & gas and geology consultant. University website (webarchived), Research gate (webarchived), Teaching Exploration and Production Training Services website (webarchived), University Catalogus Professorum (webarchived).</p>
Wageningen University & Research	Shell	<p>Peter J Boogaard worked as a toxicologist with Shell between 1996 and 2021 and was the Chair of the Toxicology Group of Concawe 2006-2021. From 2016 - 2023, Boogaard was seconded by Shell as the Special Chair Environmental health and human biomonitoring of contaminants, embedded at the WUR Unit Agrotechnology and Food. While the special chair ended in 2023, Boogaard is still associated with the WUR. LinkedIn page, University webpage (webarchived), profile in Chemie Magazine december 2017, Interview in campus newspaper Resource.</p>
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	Gasunie	<p>The chair of Hans van Koningsbrugge, History and Politics of Russia, was sponsored by Gasunie. Financing of Gasunie was not mentioned on his profile page. Volkskrant article, Website of Russian Centre at RUG (webarchived) Contract (from freedom of information request to RUG) Profile page in university website (webarchived).</p>
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	Gasunie	<p>Gasunie financed a part time research chair (<i>bijzondere hoogleraarstoel</i>) "Geopolitics and Energy Transition" at the RUG, held by Coby van der Linde. The chair had been created by Gasunie in 2003/2004 and ended in 2015, but was restarted in 2017 "considering developments in the international markets of oil and gas within the Doctrine of International Relations (IB) play an increasingly prominent role". "The Chair in Geopolitics and Energy Transition focuses on the force field between traditional power politics, global market forces and sustainability debates. In doing so, the chair focuses in particular on the study of international oil and gas markets in relation to relations between countries, international organisations (in particular the EU and the International Energy Agency) and business."</p> <p>At the same time, Coby van der Linde had various ties to oil and gas companies and lobby groups, a Saudi research organisation, and in addition was director of an energy policy thinktank. Journalists from Nieuwsuur wrote about the lack of transparency and apparent conflicts of interests of Coby van der Linde. In 2018, the <i>bijzondere hoogleraarstoel</i> was transformed into a regular research chair, which, however, still received funding from Gasunie, which was not mentioned on the university website. The financing of Gasunie for the endowed research chair of Coby van der Linde was supposed to be extended until 27 May 2024, but Coby van der Linde terminated her contract in October 2022. Contract for bijzondere hoogleraarstoel, Contract for gewone hoogleraarstoel (1), Contract for gewone hoogleraarstoel (2), Nieuwsuur item, CIEP website (webarchived).</p>

Table 5: Academic staff, board or committee members with additional (advisory) role for fossil(-related) company in 2022-2025

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Partner	Description
TU Delft	Gasunie	Rector Tim van der Hagen is part of the Gasunie supervisory board. Until end of 2023 he was on the board of the Netherlands Energy Research Alliance, and of the Grow Foundation. Gasunie website (webarchived) , University website (webarchived) .
TU Delft	Shell	Wijnand Veeneman is Associate Professor Organisation and Management at TUD, researching public transport, and scientific director of NGInfra, a public-private consortium around infrastructure. According to his LinkedIn he "develops for and teaches courses at Shell aimed at project managers on the decision-making and stakeholder engagement in development process of complex oil and gas projects and he teaches these regularly across the globe". LinkedIn page (archived) , CV , Volkskrant article (archived) .
TU Delft	Binga Energy	Pacelli Zitha was Professor of Oil and Gas Production Engineering at TU Delft and Founder of Binga Energy. This was listed as an ancilliary activity on the TUD website. He passed away in February 2024. University website (webarchived) , Binga Energy website (webarchived) .
Universiteit Twente	Shell	According to his biography on the University of Twente website, Dr. Sascha Kersten is professor of Sustainable Process Technology at University of Twente and Teacher at Shell training centre. University website (webarchived) .
Universiteit Twente	Shell	Floor de Jong is Business Advisor to Shell Group CIO and was listed as a member of the advisory board of the Business & IT study program at the UT in 2023 (removed in 2025). University website (webarchived) .
Universiteit Twente	TotalEnergies	Prof. Rohlfs provides consulting services to TotalEnergies. University website (webarchived) .
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen	Shell, Gasunie	The Advisory Board of the executive MBA Energy Transition includes Ruud de Jongh, Vice President Gas & Hydrogen Partnerships Shell Nederland, and Hans Coenen, Vice president corporate strategy and business development at Gasunie, are a members (the latter did a promotional video for the MBA) University website (webarchived) , New Energy Business School website (webarchived) .
Rijksuniversiteit Groningen and Dutch research funding agency (<i>Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek</i> , NWO)	RJBC Arctic & Energy, Shell	The chair of the NWO programme committee Netherlands Polar Programme and guest lecturer at RUG, Robert Blaauw, has a consultancy in the fields of "arctic projects, oil and gas industry, sustainable development". Blaauw's LinkedIn summary describes his "36 years experience in Shell in the international upstream oil and gas business". University website (webarchived) , Information from Dutch Business Registry (Kamer van Koophandel, KvK) LinkedIn page , FtM article , NWO website (webarchived) .
Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam	Aramco, Shell, Petrobras, Vale	Cees Van Riel, professor of corporate communication at RSM, has been hired for branding-related consultancy work by various fossil fuel companies, including Petrobras, Saudi Aramco, Vale, and Shell. Shell and Petrobras were executive members of the communication network of his consulting firm (the Reputation Insititute, now Rep-Trak). Van Riel founded a peer-reviewed journal in 1997, which has received financial support from Shell, and the "Reputation forum The Netherlands", of which Shell is a member. Changerism report A Pipeline of Ideas Rep-Trak website (archived) , University website (webarchived) , managementboek.nl interview (archived) .
Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam	Shell	The founder of the DRIFT sustainability transition institute and authority in the Netherlands on transition science, Jan Rotmans, has done consulting work for Shell. Website Jan Rotmans (archived) University website (archived) , Interview on MT Sprout (webarchived) .

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Table 5 – continued from previous page

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Partner	Description
Universiteit Utrecht	IFP Energies Nouvelles	Prof Dr Fadi Nader is leader of research projects at <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles (Institut Français du Pétrole, IFP)</i> . <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles</i> is an institute researching i.a. oil and gas production, funded by both the French state and industry (industry accounts for the majority of total budget). University website (webarchived) , Ancillary activities on university website (webarchived) , Researchgate profile (webarchived) , IFPEN website (webarchived) , Press release IFPEN (webarchived) .
Universiteit Utrecht	Shell	Gert Jan Kramer was Manager Energy Futures at Shell from 2010 to 2016 at the same time as being part-time Professor at Leiden University. He is now professor of Sustainable Energy Supply Systems at the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development at UU and he is advisor to Curoil (distributor of oil and gas). Before 2010, he was part-time professor at TU/e while also working at Shell. On his UU profile, he links to a free ebook from Shell which he edited while working at Shell and Leiden University which includes "36 thought-provoking essays about the many energy challenges society faces in the coming decades" by 55 "thought leaders in industry, government and academia". The book was offered for free, because "energy transition challenges merit an informed debate". Another LU professor was one of the authors who contributed to the Shell book. The announcement of this on the LU website does not mention that the book was published by Shell. Essays from this book are still being used in 2024/2025 in the UU course Sustainable Energy Supply and Gert Jan Kramer refers to this e-book on his UU profile page. Coby van der Linde (RUG and Gasunie) also contributed to the book. University website (webarchived) , Shell website (webarchived) , Booktopia about Shell book , facebook post with photo of king Willem-Alexander .
Universiteit Utrecht	World Petroleum Council - NL	Petra de Jongh was on the World Petroleum Council - NL in 2021 and 2022. She has filed patents together with Shell, Total and BP - for example, recently with BP in 2023 and with Total Marketing Services in 2016. In September 2024, de Jongh justified starting a new research project with BP on liquid fuels by saying: "BP is one of the top-four major oil companies in terms of climate. The company is making major investments in renewable energy. This is a company we can work with." University website (webarchived) , World Petroleum Council Excellence Awards 2021 (webarchived) , Example of WPC activities in 2020 (webarchived) , Advalvas (webarchived) . Patent with Total , Patent with BP , Advalvas (webarchived) .
Leiden Universiteit	Shell	Drs. Kenan Yildirim is a member of the board of governors of Leiden University, while at the same time being Finance Director of Shell Nederland and managing director at Shell Pensioenbureau Nederland B.V. University press release (archived) , LinkedIn page .
Leiden Universiteit	Shell	On the LU committee to review collaborations with fossil industry sits Irene Groot, who currently works with Shell and the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) on the production of synthetic fuels. She also sits on the board of the Dutch Catalysis Society, together with someone from Shell. Irene Groot published about work supported by Sasol and Sabic in 2024, 2023 and 2022. Dutch Catalysis Society website , University website .

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Table 5 – continued from previous page

University	Fossil Fuel Industry Partner	Description
<p>Dutch research funding agency (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek, NWO)</p>	<p>Shell</p>	<p>Ewald Breunese and Peter Veenstra served on an NWA–NWO grant committee (NWA–ORC 2019, 2020/21, and 2022; potentially extending beyond 2022, although the committee members for later years have not yet been published). This committee determines which research projects in NWA-ORC receive funding. Ewald Breunese is a former Shell employee, listed as retired in the NWA-ORC round 2019 commission members list, but still listed as Manager Energy Transitions at Shell in May 2020 at e.g. an event of the World Petroleum Council-NL. Peter Veenstra has been with Shell for nearly four decades and currently holds the position of Senior Principal Science Expert. NWA-ORC committee 2022 (webarchived) NWA-ORC committee 2020/21 (webarchived), NWA-ORC committee 2019 (webarchived), World Petroleum Council Expert Workshop (webarchived).</p>
<p>Dutch research funding agency (Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek, NWO)</p>	<p>Gasunie</p>	<p>Drs. Dirk Jan van den Berg served as a non-executive director at Gasunie from 2014 to 2023, while also holding the position of chair of the supervisory board of the Dutch Research Council (NWO) from April 2020 onward. LinkedIn page, NWO website (webarchived).</p>

Appendix B. Email sent to Dutch academic institutions

Email to NWO, Universiteiten van Nederland, TU Delft, TU Eindhoven, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Wageningen University & Research, and the Universities of Utrecht, Leiden, Maastricht, Amsterdam, Twente, and Tilburg (September 2024)

Geachte [naam],

Ik ben betrokken bij Solid Sustainability Research. Vanuit de Universiteit Leiden hebben wij een projectsubsidie ontvangen om te onderzoeken welke lessen kunnen worden getrokken uit het beëindigen van samenwerkingen tussen de tabaksindustrie en universiteiten.

Binnen dit project onderzoeken we wanneer en waarom samenwerkingen zijn beëindigd, of dit is vastgelegd in beleid, en of dit beleid effectief is. Dit onderzoek voeren we uit met het oog op de huidige relaties tussen universiteiten en de fossiele industrie.

In dit kader zouden wij graag willen weten:

- Of de [universiteit/organisatie] een beleid heeft met betrekking tot samenwerking met de tabaksindustrie.
- Zo ja, sinds wanneer dit beleid is geïmplementeerd.
- En hoe dit beleid wordt gecommuniceerd naar alle universiteitsmedewerkers.

De resultaten van ons onderzoek kunnen mogelijk bijdragen aan het opstellen van duidelijke kaders voor toekomstige samenwerkingen, bijvoorbeeld met de fossiele industrie.

Wij stellen uw medewerking zeer op prijs en danken u alvast hartelijk voor uw tijd.

Met vriendelijke groet,

Lynn Vanheule
Solid Sustainability Research
<https://www.solid-sustainability.org/>

Follow-up email to the above universities after receiving clarifying questions, November 2024

L.S.,

Begin september ontving u een email met de vraag of uw universiteit beleid heeft met betrekking tot samenwerkingen met de tabaksindustrie. Wij hebben begrepen dat dit bij een aantal universiteiten vragen heeft opgeroepen en dat het onduidelijk was wat de rol van de Universiteit Leiden zou zijn. Als hoofdaanvrager van de **LHSC-beurs** waarbinnen dit onderzoek plaatsvindt, geef ik graag wat extra toelichting om eventuele misverstanden uit de weg te helpen.

Met een kleine booster-beurs van het Leiden Healthy Society Center (4000 euro, looptijd tot eind december 2024) heeft dit project als doel een historische tijdslijn te schetsen van samenwerkingen tussen wetenschappers en de tabaksindustrie. Een van de hoofdvragen hiervan luidt: "In hoeverre is er formeel beleid ontwikkeld met betrekking tot samenwerkingen tussen academische instellingen en de tabaksindustrie, en welke andere factoren hebben bijgedragen aan het beëindigen van deze samenwerkingen?". Voor dit onderzoek werken we o.a. samen met maatschappelijke partner **Solid Sustainability Research**.

Als start van dit onderzoek begonnen we met het zoeken naar publieke beleidsdocumenten op universitaire website. In tegenstelling tot onze originele onderzoekshypothese (dat universitair beleid een sleutelrol heeft gespeeld in de maatschappelijke afkeuring van tabaks-samenwerkingen), konden we zulke documenten niet vinden. Om er zeker van te zijn dat we geen publieke documenten hebben gemist, hebben we (via de mail die u ontving) navraag gedaan. Hierbij had vermeld moeten worden dat we op zoek zijn naar publiek beschikbare beleids- of communicatiedocumenten.

Op basis van deze bevindingen is onze voorlopige onderzoeksconclusie dat universitair beleid geen grote rol heeft gespeeld in de veranderende kijk op tabakssamenwerkingen. In plaats daarvan lijkt beleid vanuit beroepsverenigingen (zoals de Nederlandse Vereniging voor Oncologie), wetenschappelijke tijdschriften (zoals de **British Medical Journal**), en financieringsfondsen (zoals het **KWF**) cruciaal te zijn geweest. Onze aanbevelingen voor toekomstig onderzoek zullen zijn om enerzijds de rol van deze spelers verder uit te lichten, en anderzijds om tabakssamenwerkingen mee te nemen in huidige discussies over universitaire samenwerkingen met verschillende externe partners.

Ik wil u graag hartelijk danken voor uw medewerking aan dit project. Deze bevindingen zullen na de looptijd hiervan worden samengevat, en ik stuur u tzt graag het onderzoek-rapport op. We hopen hiermee een kleine bijdrage te kunnen leveren aan een goed geïnformeerde discussie over universitaire samenwerking met externe partners.

Mocht u nog vragen hebben over deze samenwerking of de onderzoeksmethodiek, dan hoor ik graag van u.

Met vriendelijke groet,

Anne E. Urai, PhD

Assistant Professor, Cognitive Psychology, Leiden University

Email to Radboud University & Universiteit voor Humanistiek (21 February 2025)

Beste [Radboud Universiteit/UvH],

Als onderzoeker bij de Universiteit Leiden heb ik, samen met maatschappelijke partner Solid Sustainability Research, een **projectsubsidie** ontvangen om te onderzoeken welke lessen kunnen worden getrokken uit het beëindigen van samenwerkingen tussen de tabaksindustrie en universiteiten.

Binnen dit project onderzoeken we wanneer en waarom samenwerkingen zijn beëindigd, of dit is vastgelegd in beleid, en of dit beleid effectief is. Dit onderzoek voeren we uit met het oog op de huidige relaties tussen universiteiten en de fossiele industrie.

In dit kader zouden wij graag willen weten:

- Of de [Radboud Universiteit/UvH] een beleid heeft met betrekking tot samenwerking met de tabaksindustrie.
- Zo ja, sinds wanneer dit beleid is geïmplementeerd.
- En hoe dit beleid wordt gecommuniceerd naar alle universiteitsmedewerkers.

Voor dit kleine project zijn we alleen op zoek naar publiek beschikbare beleids- of communicatiedocumenten. Omdat we op uw website geen specifieke documenten konden vinden, doen we graag navraag of zulke documenten inderdaad niet bestaan.

De resultaten van ons onderzoek kunnen mogelijk bijdragen aan het opstellen van duidelijke kaders voor toekomstige samenwerkingen, bijvoorbeeld met de fossiele industrie. Wij stellen uw medewerking zeer op prijs en danken u alvast hartelijk voor uw tijd.

Met vriendelijke groet,

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